

1 **An Integrated Multidimensional Resilience Index for urban**
2 **areas prone to flash floods: development and validation**

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14 **HIGHLIGHTS**

- 15 • Resilience analysis is key to developing flood risk reduction strategies.
- 16 • The development of the Integrated Multidimensional Resilience Index
17 followed a multidimensional approach.
- 18 • The methodology identified underlying characteristics that determine
19 urban system resilience.
- 20 • Internal validation through uncertainty and sensitivity analyses yields
21 sources of index variability and robustness.
- 22 • Resilience spatial pattern identification supports more efficient resource
23 allocation for flood risk mitigation.
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26 **GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT**

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29 **ABSTRACT**

30 Resilience analysis is critical in developing flash flood risk reduction strategies in
31 the context of global change and sustainable development. The most common
32 method for assessing resilience is index-based. Nevertheless, the resulting
33 indices typically fail to represent resilience's multidimensional character since
34 they frequently disregard all involved dimensions (i.e., social, economic,
35 environmental, physical, institutional, and cultural). Furthermore, regional
36 resilience indices are rarely externally validated in urban areas prone to flash
37 flooding because the required data are limited and flash flooding does not occur
38 concurrently throughout the study region. This research developed and validated
39 a regional Integrated Multidimensional Resilience Index (IMRI) in urban flash
40 flood-prone areas to address the aforementioned knowledge gaps. The Monte
41 Carlo method enabled internal validation of the IMRI following uncertainty and
42 sensitivity analyses. Latent Class Cluster Analysis (LCCA) was used to
43 characterize resilience, leveraging resulting regional spatial patterns. The
44 findings obtained revealed that the most resilient urban areas have greater social

45 and cultural resilience, while the least resilient urban areas should strengthen
46 their social and institutional resilience. Validation results demonstrated a low bias
47 between the IMRI scores and the control statistics derived from the Monte Carlo
48 analysis as well as a higher than 80% probability of not getting variations in the
49 resilience categories, confirming the robustness of the IMRI. Through LCCA, five
50 distinct regional spatial patterns of resilience were identified. The methodological
51 approach deployed here enabled the identification of the underlying
52 characteristics that determine the urban system's resilience to flash flooding,
53 thereby supporting the formulation of resilience-building strategies for each
54 dimension and urban area under consideration.

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56 **Keywords**

57 Resilience; Flash flooding; Sensitivity analysis; Uncertainty; Flood risk
58 management; Multidimensional approach.

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70 **1. Introduction**

71 Floods are becoming increasingly frequent and severe, posing a worldwide risk
72 to urban areas and societies (Batista and Gourbesville, 2016; Rana et al., 2021;
73 Khan et al., 2022). According to the Centre for Research on the Epidemiology of
74 Disasters (CRED), there were 37% more floods in 2021 than the yearly average
75 for the previous two decades (2001-2020), resulting in 4,143 deaths, 29.2 million
76 people impacted, and US\$74.4 billion in direct economic damages (CRED,
77 2021). In particular, flash floods are the deadliest type of flood owing to their fast
78 onset, i.e., less than six hours' warning (Borga et al., 2011). Flash floods
79 commonly occur in mountainous areas, where about one billion people live (Wyss
80 et al., 2022), which means that flood risk mitigation in this context is vital to public
81 safety management and social development (Borga et al., 2011).

82

83 Climate change-induced hydrological cycle intensification, unplanned occupation
84 of flood-prone areas, demographic pressure, land-use changes, and ecosystem
85 degradation are likely to increase flood risk over the coming decades (Marzi et
86 al., 2019; Fekete et al., 2020; Leandro et al., 2020). Despite significant
87 investments in flood risk mitigation, flood damage is still rising (Feldmeyer et al.,
88 2021). This demonstrates that conventional flood risk management strategies,
89 which rely on flood-control infrastructures like levees supplemented with non-
90 structural measures such as land-use planning or early warning systems, are
91 neither a guarantee of total protection nor sufficient to deal with future
92 uncertainties (Kotzee and Reyers, 2016; Fekete et al., 2020). Furthermore, these
93 flood-control infrastructures have disturbed many rivers' hydrological regimes and
94 reduced or suppressed lateral connectivity within river systems, degrading fluvial

95 ecosystems and jeopardizing their capacity to provide ecosystem services (Liao,
96 2012).

97

98 Consequently, urban areas require a paradigm shift from a resistance-based
99 approach to a proactive resilience-based strategy that minimizes flood risk while
100 conserving and restoring river ecosystems for sustainable development and
101 climate change adaptation (Mayunga, 2007; Liao, 2012). Throughout the past two
102 decades, a number of agreements, strategies, policies, and frameworks have
103 emphasized the need to harmonize these often conflicting objectives in order to
104 strengthen urban-social systems resilience and mitigate flood risk.

105

106 At the international level, the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction
107 2015–2030 emphasizes the need to integrate social, economic, structural,
108 cultural, environmental, and institutional dimensions to improve preparedness for
109 response and recovery and strengthen resilience. The 2030 Agenda for
110 Sustainable Development and its 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)
111 address the major global challenges facing humanity today. Within the scope of
112 this research, SDG1 (target 1.5) stresses building the resilience of vulnerable
113 societies and reducing their exposure and vulnerability to natural disasters; SDG3
114 (target 3.d) emphasizes strengthening society's capacity for early warning
115 systems and risk reduction and management; SDG6 (target 6.6) seeks to protect
116 and restore aquatic ecosystems; SDG11 (target 11.5) addresses the need to
117 reduce natural disaster damage, and target 11.b emphasizes the importance of
118 developing and implementing a holistic disaster risk management strategy; and
119 SDG13 (target 13.1) urges strengthening resilience and adaptive capacity to

120 climate-related natural disasters. Additional normative instruments include the
121 "Making Cities Resilient" initiative, which 1,504 cities worldwide have signed to
122 make cities inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable by 2030.

123

124 At the European level, the Strategic Agenda for 2019–2024 emphasizes the
125 European Union's (EU) commitment to strengthen resilience against natural
126 disasters, prevent biodiversity loss, and protect environmental systems (main
127 priorities 1 and 3, respectively) through integrated and resilience-based risk
128 management. The objectives of the Green Deal and Climate Action are supported
129 by the VIII Environment Action Programme 2021–2030. Priority thematic
130 objectives of this program include objective 2, which pledges to improve adaptive
131 capacity, strengthen resilience, and reduce vulnerability to climate-related natural
132 disasters; and objective 5, which is committed to protecting, conserving, and
133 restoring aquatic ecosystem biodiversity and improving its state and services.

134

135 Given the foregoing, assessing resilience is critical for developing disaster risk
136 reduction strategies in the context of global change (Rana et al., 2021).
137 Resilience can be evaluated from both an engineering and an ecological
138 standpoint, although the latter has come to dominate in flood risk management
139 (Mayunga, 2007; Liao, 2012). In this context, resilience refers to a social-urban
140 system's ability to respond to and recover from flood disasters, which includes
141 inherent conditions that allow the system to absorb impacts and cope with a flood
142 event, as well as post-event adaptive processes that allow the system to
143 reorganize, change, and learn in response to a flood (Fekete et al., 2020).

144 The resilience concept's complexity makes proposing a standard mechanism for
145 its measurement and operationalization challenging for scientists, practitioners,
146 or decision-makers (Feldmeyer et al., 2021). As resilience cannot be directly
147 measured, indices based on a set of indicators (or proxies) that capture the
148 urban-social system's underlying structure are the most frequent way of analysing
149 resilience (Liao, 2012; Feldmeyer et al., 2021). For a comprehensive analysis
150 and effective flood risk reduction strategies, the methodology to be applied must
151 capture resilience's multifaceted nature (Liao, 2012; Rana et al., 2021).
152 Accordingly, to assess resilience, it's imperative to include social, economic,
153 ecosystem, physical, institutional, and cultural dimensions (Qasim et al., 2016;
154 Rana et al., 2021; Khan et al., 2022;).

155

156 Social resilience is determined by population structure, social networks, norms,
157 customs, and social organizations (Adger, 2000). Economic resilience is
158 characterized by employment, income, savings, or potential business disruption,
159 and it includes society's financial resources to absorb and recover from flood
160 losses (Rose, 2004). Ecosystem resilience encompasses natural resources and
161 ecosystems, including their functions and services, which are crucial to society's
162 well-being and adaptability to future environmental conditions (Sherrieb et al.,
163 2010; Liao, 2012). Lifeline infrastructures, transportation networks, and housing
164 characteristics are indicators of urban physical resilience (Birkmann et al., 2013).
165 Institutional resilience is related to the structure of institutions, management
166 procedures, or political systems that control society's response to flood events
167 (Tierney, 2012). Finally, the tangible and intangible aspects of cultural goods,

168 such as monuments, cultural interest sites, and cultural traditions, are part of
169 cultural resilience (Vojinovic et al., 2016).

170

171 In recent decades, resilience indexes for natural disasters have proliferated,
172 including the Community Disaster Resilience Index (CDRI) by Mayunga (2007),
173 the Baseline Resilience Indicators for Communities (BRIC) by Cutter et al. (2010),
174 the Community Resilience Index (CRI) by Sherrieb et al. (2010), the Open
175 Resilience Index (ORI) by Feldmeyer et al. (2021), or the Natural Disaster
176 Resilience Index (NDRI) by Khan et al. (2022). Concerning flash floods, studies
177 have taken fragmented approaches to deal with resilience's multidimensionality.
178 As examples, Oliver et al. (2019) created a Resilience Index based on flash flood
179 societal perceptions. Islam et al. (2020) proposed a Resilience Status Index
180 based on the probability of flash flood events and five resilience indicators derived
181 from field surveys. While omitting the cultural dimension from resilience research,
182 Moghadas et al. (2019) used an index-based approach to integrate social,
183 economic, physical, environmental, and institutional dimensions. Consequently,
184 to the best of our knowledge, no prior publication on flash flood resilience has
185 covered all dimensions of resilience pertaining to flash floods.

186

187 Furthermore, resilience indices for flood-prone areas are often not validated.
188 When testing flood resilience indices, a prevalent method is to utilize a proxy,
189 such as the areas previously flooded by other events (Chun et al., 2017) or the
190 number of fatalities and affected individuals resulting from floods (Feldmeyer et
191 al., 2021). Another typical validation method is correlation with other published
192 indices (Moghadas et al., 2019). These two procedures are known as external

193 validation and cross-validation, respectively. Internal validation methods, such as
194 that proposed by Renald et al. (2016), using confirmatory factor analysis, or that
195 proposed here, based on uncertainty and sensitivity analyses using the Monte
196 Carlo method (Aroca-Jiménez et al., 2020, 2022), offer better alternatives for
197 validating regional flash flood resilience indices.

198

199 To address the aforementioned knowledge gaps, this research proposes for the
200 first time the construction and validation of an Integrated Multidimensional
201 Resilience Index (IMRI) in urban areas prone to flash flooding using a
202 comprehensively holistic approach. To do this, a resilience database comprising
203 indicators for social, economic, ecosystem, physical, institutional, and cultural
204 dimensions was compiled. Resilience factors for each dimension were found
205 using Hierarchical Segmentation Analysis (HSA) and Principal Component
206 Analysis (PCA). The IMRI was then analyzed for uncertainty and sensitivity using
207 a Monte Carlo model. The uncertainty analysis calculated the bias between the
208 original IMRI scores and the median and median absolute deviation (MAD)
209 obtained from the Monte Carlo analysis, as well as the probability of having
210 changes in the IMRI category when this median and MAD were employed instead
211 of the original IMRI scores. The Monte Carlo analysis also provided sensitivity
212 tornado plots for the sensitivity analysis. Finally, Latent Class Cluster Analysis
213 (LCCA) was utilized to determine regional resilience spatial patterns.

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218 **2. Methodology**

219 *2.1 Study area*

220 Castilla y León is located in the northwest of Spain, between 40° 05' and 43° 14'
221 north latitude and 1° 46' and 7° 05' west longitude (Fig. 1). Castilla y León is the
222 largest region in Spain and one of the largest in Europe, with a total area of 94,226
223 km². Its orography consists primarily of a plateau (700–1,100 m.a.s.l.) surrounded
224 by mountain ranges that can surpass 2,500 m.a.s.l., resulting in significant rainfall
225 gradients from the centre (400 mm/year) to the periphery (1,000–1,500 mm/year).
226 This steep terrain may prompt a quick hydrologic response to intense rainfall
227 events, which may cause flash floods (Bodoque et al., 2015).

228

229

230 **Fig. 1.** Location of the study region (Castilla y León, Spain) and flash flood-prone
231 urban areas considered in resilience analysis (areas colored in yellow). ASPRFs:
232 Areas with a Significant Potential Risk of Flooding.

233

234 Castilla y León has a population density of 25.3 inhabitants per km² (statistics for
235 2021), which is lower than Spain's overall population density (93.5 inhabitants
236 per km²). 71% of Castilla y León municipalities are severely depopulated, defined

237 as less than 10 persons per km². Seventy percent of the region's urban areas
238 prone to flash floods (40 of the 57 evaluated) do not reach this population density
239 threshold. Moreover, the over-aging and dependence rates in these urban areas
240 are 37% and 60.5%, respectively.

241

242 The average net income per person in the target urban areas is 12,386 euros,
243 and the average Gini coefficient is 28.6%. Even though the service sector
244 dominates in these communities, 37% of workers are employed in other
245 economic sectors. In these urban areas, the average municipal budget per
246 person is 1,513 euros, whereas the average direct income per inhabitant (i.e.,
247 through municipal taxes) is 473 euros.

248

249 Flash flood-prone municipalities include about 11% of Castilla y León's protected
250 natural areas. Riparian vegetation covers 49.7% of these communities' urban
251 floodplains, although 43.5% are under pressure (i.e., urban, agricultural, or
252 hydrogeomorphological). According to the Water Framework Directive, 56.1%
253 and 96.6% of the streams passing through the localities of interest are in good
254 ecological and chemical status, respectively.

255

256 Decades of population decline in Castilla y León municipalities have resulted in
257 a loss of economic empowerment, reducing their capacity to provide essential
258 public services and maintain vital public infrastructures. On average, 10
259 kilometres separate the areas of interest from the nearest health centre, whereas
260 41 kilometres separate them from the nearest hospital. In these urban areas, an
261 estimated 83% of the dwellings are in good condition, and 77% have two or more

262 storeys above ground. In the urban areas of interest, 7.6% of all dwellings are in
263 floodplains.

264

265 Seven percent of the urban areas prone to flash floods assessed in this study
266 have a local flood action plan, although the Civil Protection Plan for Flood Risk of
267 Castilla y León does not mandate it for any of the 57 municipalities examined in
268 this research. In addition, local spending on security forces and emergency
269 management amounted to 3.1% of total expenditures in the municipalities of
270 interest, while that on education was at 2.8%.

271

272 Lastly, 6.6% of the total number of cultural assets in the region are located in
273 municipalities prone to flash flooding, and 1.2% of them are situated in their
274 floodplains. Moreover, 65 % of the cultural assets located in the target urban
275 areas are in excellent condition, and in 67 % of the cases, water-resistant building
276 materials prevail.

277

278 *2.2 Resilience analysis*

279 The following steps comprise the approach adopted here: 1) the identification of
280 urban areas prone to flash flooding; 2) the development of a database containing
281 resilience indicators; 3) the identification of resilience factors; 4) the construction
282 of the Integrated Multidimensional Resilience Index (IMRI); 5) an internal
283 validation of the IMRI through uncertainty and sensitivity analyses; and 6) the
284 identification of regional spatial patterns of resilience (Fig. 2).

285

286

287 **Fig. 2.** Graphical overview of the different stages of the implemented
 288 methodology.

289

290 *2.2.1 Identifying flash flood-prone urban areas*

291 Not all Castilla y León municipalities are prone to flash flooding, so we first
 292 determined the urban areas that may be impacted by this type of natural hazard
 293 by considering the following requirements: i) the longitudinal slope of the
 294 watercourses that crossed the urban centres must be equal to or greater than
 295 0.01 m/m, which is a threshold commonly used in the definition of mountain

296 streams (Bodoque et al., 2015); ii) these previously identified watercourses must
297 be catalogued as Areas with a Significant Potential Risk of Flooding, ASPRFs;
298 and iii) the urban areas affected by the above-mentioned rivers must be
299 potentially influenced by flood-prone areas with a low probability of flooding, i.e.,
300 500-year flood. The GIS layers utilized to apply the latter two criteria were
301 established in accordance with the provisions of the EU Floods Directive
302 (2007/60/EC). Accordingly, 57 municipalities were considered in the resilience
303 analysis (Fig. 1).

304

305 *2.2.2 Database development*

306 Following a thorough review of the existing literature and a consideration of the
307 study region's unique context, a total of 191 resilience indicators were initially
308 identified, and of these, 48 corresponded to social resilience, 32 to economic
309 resilience, 34 to ecosystem resilience, 44 to physical resilience, 27 to institutional
310 resilience, and 6 to cultural resilience. The database, which contains these
311 resilience indicators and associated descriptive information (e.g., data sources,
312 data reference years, variable descriptions), is accessible in an open access
313 repository (Aroca-Jiménez et al., 2023).

314

315 The z-score method was used to standardize the variables, which involved
316 rescaling them in such a manner that their mean was 0 and their standard
317 deviation was 1. To find duplicate variables, correlation matrices were generated
318 for each resilience dimension (Aroca-Jiménez et al., 2020). As a result, the social
319 dimension was reduced to 45 variables, the economic dimension to 29, and the

320 environmental dimension to 33. The number of variables in the other dimensions
321 (physical, institutional, and cultural) remained unchanged.

322

323 *2.2.3 Identification of resilience factors*

324 The most frequently used methodological approach for developing resilience
325 indices is to employ a Principal Components Analysis (PCA) to reduce the initial
326 collection of variables by combining them. This statistical technique, however,
327 has a major constraint related to the ratio of variables to analysis units (in this
328 case, the municipality) investigated. When this ratio is less than 3, it is not
329 advisable to use a PCA (Trninic et al., 2012). The cultural dimension was
330 unaffected by this hypothesis, but the social, economic, environmental, physical,
331 and institutional dimensions needed the use of a Hierarchical Segmentation
332 Analysis (HSA) to identify resilience factors afterwards.

333

334 HSA is a multivariate statistical technique aimed to split a collection of variables
335 into groups so that variables within the same group are as similar as possible
336 (i.e., minimal distance) and variables within other groups are as dissimilar as
337 possible (i.e., maximum distance; Sarstedt and Mooi, 2014). The squared
338 Euclidean distance was obtained from the sum of the differences between
339 squared pairs of values as a distance or dissimilarity metric. Ward's method was
340 viewed as a clustering technique that used hierarchical algorithms and sought the
341 lowest possible variance or variability within each group (Sarstedt and Mooi,
342 2014). This technique is regarded as among the most efficient, particularly when
343 the sample size is small (Martín et al., 2015). Utilizing the dendrogram (graphical

344 output of the HSA), the best number of groups into which to split the social,
345 economic, ecosystem, physical, and institutional factors was determined.

346

347 After subdividing the original variables into smaller groups, a PCA was performed
348 on each of them in order to subsequently calculate the resilience index. PCA is a
349 multivariate statistical analysis technique that aims to explain a large number of
350 observable variables using a set of unknown variables called principal
351 components or factors. They were derived from the linear combination of
352 observable variables and explained as much of their variance as possible
353 (Sarstedt and Mooi, 2014). Using the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) statistic and
354 Bartlett's test for sphericity, it was determined whether the variables were
355 sufficiently correlated for PCA ($KMO \geq 0.5$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.05$, respectively). Those
356 variables with communalities (i.e., a proportion of each variable's variance that
357 can be explained by identifiable factors) below 0.30 were omitted. The factor
358 loadings revealed the correlation (ranging from -1 to 1) between the original
359 variables and the resulting factors. These factor loadings' values and signs
360 (positive or negative) enabled us to determine the different resilience factors. The
361 factor scores, which were values assigned to each analysis unit by the different
362 factors, were then calculated using the regression method and subsequently
363 included into the resilience index.

364

365 *2.2.4 Construction of the Integrated Multidimensional Resilience Index (IMRI)*

366 As explained in the preceding section, the Integrated Multidimensional Resilience
367 Index (IMRI) was developed from the factor scores, which were typified by a
368 mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 1. Consequently, municipalities with

369 positive factor values were more resilient than the mean, while municipalities with
370 negative factor scores were less resilient than the mean.

371

372 The IMRI score for each municipality was determined using the following
373 equation:

$$IMRI = R_{Soc} + R_{Econ} + R_{Ecos} + R_{Phy} + R_{Ins} + R_{Cul} \quad (1)$$

374 Where R_{Soc} is the social resilience, R_{Econ} is the economic resilience, R_{Ecos} is the
375 ecosystem resilience, R_{Phy} is the physical resilience, R_{Ins} is the institutional
376 resilience, and R_{Cul} is the cultural resilience. The score for each dimension was
377 calculated as follows:

$$R_D = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^f (w_f \cdot P_f)}{\sum_{i=1}^f w_f} \quad (2)$$

378 Where R_D is the resilience of a certain dimension (social, economic, ecosystem,
379 physical, institutional, or cultural), w_f is the weight associated with a certain
380 resilience factor, and P_f represent the factor scores of that resilience factor (see
381 section 2.2.3).

382

383 The weight assigned to each resilience factor (w_f) was determined by the
384 tolerance statistic, which was derived from a regression analysis that
385 incorporated the factors underlying each dimension. This statistic allowed us to
386 identify multicollinearity among the various factors (Sarstedt and Mooi, 2014). In
387 the IMRI, factors with weaker correlations to the other factors were assigned a
388 greater weight, while those with stronger correlations were assigned a smaller
389 weight (Aroca-Jiménez et al., 2022).

390

391

392 *2.2.5 IMRI validation: Uncertainty and sensitivity analyses*

393 The IMRI was internally validated through uncertainty and sensitivity analyses.
394 An uncertainty analysis was conducted to assess the robustness of the IMRI's
395 resilience categories, and a sensitivity analysis was performed to determine
396 which index inputs had the most influence on the variability of the different outputs
397 (Tate, 2012). The IMRI was internally validated in four stages: i) fitting factor
398 scores and weights to continuous probability distributions; ii) Monte Carlo
399 modeling; iii) uncertainty analysis; and iv) sensitivity analysis.

400

401 We started by fitting the factor scores and weights to several continuous
402 probability distribution functions, assuming that these values were random
403 samples from the distribution selected. The Chi-Square statistic was employed to
404 determine whether the data came from a normal distribution. If they did not, we
405 used the Anderson-Darling statistic (A^2) as a goodness-of-fit test to determine
406 which alternative distribution best matched the factor scores and weights. Finally,
407 the parameters of each probability distribution function were utilized to assess the
408 robustness of resilience factors and weights by including them as inputs in the
409 Monte Carlo simulation (Saltelli et al., 2004).

410

411 Second, the outputs of the Monte Carlo model were defined, comprising the
412 scores of the various dimensions and the IMRI scores. These new scores were
413 generated using the previously reported equations 1 and 2. The number of Monte
414 Carlo simulations required for each analysis was determined by the calculated
415 parameters (Tate, 2012). As an example, to recalculate the social dimension
416 scores, as many parameters as there were resilience factors in that dimension

417 were established, and additionally an extra parameter was necessary for the
418 weight definition. The final score for the social dimension was provided as a
419 function that would be calculated using the predetermined factors and weights.
420 The final scores for the rest of the resilience dimensions were calculated following
421 the process described above.

422

423 The median and median absolute deviation (MAD) generated by the Monte Carlo
424 model were used to assess the index uncertainty (Aroca-Jiménez et al., 2022).
425 On the one hand, both the bias between the original factor scores and the median
426 and the MAD generated from the Monte Carlo analysis were calculated. The
427 overall bias for each municipality was calculated by adding the biases for all the
428 resilience factors in the case of the IMRI, or for all the factors associated with
429 each of the resilience dimensions:

$$Bias_{(Abs)} = \sum_{i=1}^f (P_f - S) \quad (3)$$

430 Where f are the factors that compose the different dimensions and the IMRI, P_f
431 are the original factor scores, and S refers to the control statistic used (i.e.,
432 median or MAD). The relative bias ($Bias_{(Rel)}$) was calculated by dividing the value
433 of the absolute bias ($Bias_{(Abs)}$) by the number of factors involved in each case (f),
434 according to the equation:

$$Bias_{(Rel)} = \frac{Bias_{(Abs)}}{f} \quad (4)$$

435

436 In addition, for both the IMRI and the different dimensions, the uncertainty
437 associated with the selected resilience categories was estimated. Instead of the
438 original scores and weights, a new score was calculated for each municipality

439 and each resilience factor by inputting the median and the MAD resulting from
440 the Monte Carlo analysis into equation 2. Thus, we acquired as many new scores
441 as factors and weights were examined, relying on the desired outcome (i.e.,
442 dimension or IMRI scores). This allowed us to calculate the probability of a
443 municipality's resilience category changing.

444

445 Finally, a sensitivity analysis was conducted using the tornado plots generated by
446 the Monte Carlo model (Aroca-Jiménez et al., 2020, 2022). These plots allowed
447 us to determine which model inputs (i.e., resilience factors and weights) had the
448 most influence on the various modelled outcomes (i.e., IMRI or dimension
449 scores). The elements at the top of the tornado diagram had the largest impact
450 on the output scores (IMRI or dimension scores), while those at the bottom had
451 the least influence.

452

453 *2.2.6 Identifying regional spatial resilience patterns*

454 Regional spatial patterns of resilience were revealed through Latent Class
455 Cluster Analysis (LCCA). We were able to assess the spatial heterogeneity of
456 municipalities prone to flash floods based on their social, economic, ecosystem,
457 physical, institutional, and cultural resilience using this statistical method. LCCA
458 was predicated on the creation of a latent variable that reflected the underlying
459 relationships between the observable variables (i.e., the scores of the different
460 resilience dimensions). Based on the probability that a municipality belonged to
461 a specific cluster, this latent variable classified the municipalities into mutually
462 exclusive clusters. Accordingly, each cluster exhibited distinctive patterns of
463 response (Vermunt and Magidson, 2016).

464 A total of ten models were tested, ranging from all municipalities belonging to the
465 same cluster (no heterogeneity across municipalities) to municipalities being
466 divided into ten unique clusters (i.e., 10 spatial patterns). The Akaike Information
467 Criterion (AIC) was used to identify, on the basis of the model with the lowest AIC
468 value, which model best fitted the input data (i.e., dimension scores) and, hence,
469 the best number of clusters (Vermunt and Magidson, 2016).

470

471 The calculation of the parameters of the best model and associated statistics
472 allowed us to establish which dimensions were statistically significant for the
473 clustering of the municipalities (p -value < 0.05). In addition, the profile of the
474 optimal model allowed us to identify the resilience sources in each cluster and
475 the number of municipalities that composed each cluster (Aroca-Jiménez et al.,
476 2022). Alternately, the Wald test provided a pairwise comparison of the identified
477 clusters of municipalities, allowing us to assess whether clusters were statistically
478 distinct based on the scores in the different resilience dimensions (p -value < 0.05 ;
479 Vermunt and Magidson, 2016).

480

481 Analysis of variance (ANOVA) or Welch tests were conducted to determine
482 whether the differences in the IMRI scores across clusters were statistically
483 significant. Levene's test was employed to check the assumption of variance
484 homogeneity. If the significance value of this test was greater than 0.05, a one-
485 way ANOVA was performed; otherwise, a robust test of equality of means (the
486 Welch test) was undertaken. Both analyses (ANOVA and Welch test) allowed the
487 presence of statistically significant differences between cluster mean values to
488 be determined. Therefore, if the significance value of the aforesaid tests was

489 greater than 0.05, it might be stated that there were no differences. If the
490 significance value was less than 0.05, however, disparities between the cluster
491 means were established. Post-hoc analyses, Tukey's Honestly-Significant-
492 Difference test was coupled with a one-way ANOVA and a Games-Howell test
493 was paired with the Welch test, were employed to examine whether clusters of
494 urban areas differed on the basis of their IMRI (Sarstedt and Mooi, 2014).

495

496 **3. Results**

497 *3.1 Integrated Multidimensional Resilience Index (IMRI)*

498 The IMRI consisted of 37 resilience factors, of which 9 belonged to the social
499 dimension (24.3% of the total), 6 to the economic dimension (16.2%), 9 to the
500 ecosystem dimension (24.3%), 8 to the physical dimension (21.6%), 4 to the
501 institutional dimension (10.8%), and 1 to the cultural dimension (2.7%). In turn,
502 these resilience factors comprised a total of 129 variables, of which 32 were
503 associated with the social dimension (24.8% of the total), 20 with the economic
504 dimension (15.5%), 27 with the ecosystem dimension (20.9%), 32 with the
505 physical dimension (24.8%), 14 with the institutional dimension (10.9%), and 4
506 with the cultural dimension (3.1%). Fig. S1–S5 and Tables S1–S6 of the
507 supplementary material display the dendrograms generated by the HSA and the
508 statistics obtained by the PCA, respectively.

509

510 As the weights were calculated per dimension, the sum of the weights of the
511 dimensions' constituent factors was always 1. Within the social dimension, "social
512 cohesiveness and management measures" had the greatest weight (0.141),
513 while "population with adequate access to the education and health systems"

514 carried the least (0.078). The economic dimension factor with the highest weight
515 was "economic and labour diversity" (0.200), while "municipal and individual
516 economic potential" had the lowest weight (0.129). The factor with the largest
517 weight in the ecosystem dimension was "availability of water resources" (0.134),
518 while the factor with the lowest weight was "habitat fragmentation due to tourism"
519 (0.093). In the physical dimension, the factors with the greatest and lowest
520 weights were "urban facilities situated near rivers" (0.140) and "impact of floods
521 on the urban area" (0.113), respectively. In the institutional dimension, "municipal
522 flood risk management" and "municipal investment in risk management and
523 education" received the greatest weight (0.350), while "municipality's capacity to
524 cope with the occurrence of floods" and "municipality's strategy of environmental
525 awareness" received the least (0.150). The assigned weight for the cultural
526 dimension, which consisted of a single factor, was 1. In Tables S1–S5 of the
527 supplementary material, the weight associated with each resilience factor is
528 shown.

529

530 Fig. 3 displays the scores obtained for each resilience dimension for each
531 municipality of interest. The scores were divided into five groups using the
532 quintile's representation method (i.e., very high, high, medium, low, and very low).
533 The range of social dimension scores was from -0.613 to 1.357. The economic
534 dimension scores ranged from -0.574 to 0.0839. The ecosystem dimension
535 scores varied from -0.935 to 0.750. The physical dimension scores ranged from
536 -1,004 to 0.653. The range of institutional dimension scores was between -0.807
537 and 2.039. The scores for the cultural dimension fluctuated the most widely,
538 ranging from -1.256 to 3.143.

539

540 **Fig. 3.** Scores obtained in the various dimensions of urban resilience: social (a),
 541 economic (b), ecosystem (c), physical (d), institutional (e), and cultural (f).

542

543

544 Fig. 4 depicts the disaggregated IMRI scores by dimension to illustrate how each
 545 dimension contributes to the final IMRI score. Fig. 4 shows IMRI scores divided
 546 into five categories in line with the quintile's method of representation. In addition,
 547 each municipality of interest is accompanied by a radar chart in which each vertex
 548 indicates the score reached in each resilience dimension, and this is denoted by

549 the following initials: social (S), economic (E), ecosystem (H), physical (P),
 550 institutional (I), and cultural (C). As shown in Fig. 3, each point (i.e., the score in
 551 each dimension) is displayed with the colour of the category corresponding to
 552 that score to facilitate comparisons between different radar charts and, therefore,
 553 across different urban areas. Thus, dark green denotes a very high category, light
 554 green a high category, yellow a medium category, orange a low category, and red
 555 a very low category. In addition, each concentric line on the radar chart
 556 corresponds to a unique value, with the centre of the hexagon being -1.5 and the
 557 outermost line representing 2.5. The closer a location is to the centre of the radar
 558 chart, the lower the score in that dimension for that municipality (i.e., a less
 559 resilient municipality). The further away a location is from the centre of the radar
 560 chart, the higher its score in that dimension (i.e., a more resilient municipality).

561

562

563 **Fig. 4.** IMRI scores disaggregated by dimensions for each urban area of interest.

564

565

566 Fig. 4 shows that IMRI scores range from -0.409 to 1.228. In 54.5%, 45.5%, and
567 81.8% of cases, municipalities with a high IMRI score also showed strong social,
568 ecosystem, and cultural resilience, respectively. Economic resilience may be very
569 high or medium (with a frequency of 27.3% for both categories), institutional
570 resilience may be very high or high (with a frequency of 45.5% for both
571 categories), and physical resilience is often very low (with a frequency of 36.4%).
572 Municipalities with a very low IMRI score, on the other hand, had very low social
573 (58.3%), economic (41.7%), physical (33.3%), institutional (58.3%), and cultural
574 (41.7%) resilience. Furthermore, ecosystem resilience in these municipalities
575 may be very low or medium, with a frequency of 33.3% in both categories.

576

577 *3.2 Internal validation of the IMRI*

578 The scores shown in Fig. 3 and 4 represent the initial IMRI scores and the various
579 dimensions. As part of the internal validation of the IMRI, Table 1 displays the
580 regional means of the total biases, i.e., the sum of the differences between the
581 original factor scores and their respective weights and the median or MAD values
582 obtained for the same elements in the Monte Carlo analysis, expressed in
583 absolute and relative terms. The relative values were computed by dividing the
584 total biases by the number of resilience factors assessed for each dimension. The
585 total bias may be positive or negative. A positive total bias value indicated that
586 most of the factors and weights exhibited resilience above the median or MAD
587 values obtained from the Monte Carlo model, while a negative total bias value
588 indicated that most of the factors and weights indicated resilience below the
589 median or MAD values obtained from the Monte Carlo model.

590

591 Thus, the economic dimension had the greatest overall bias compared to the
 592 median (-4.016), whereas the cultural dimension had the lowest value (0.167).
 593 The economic dimension had the highest total bias from the median in relative
 594 terms (-0.669), while the ecosystem component had the lowest (-0.051). As
 595 regards the total bias from the MAD, the economic component had the greatest
 596 absolute value (-4.783), while the cultural dimension had the smallest absolute
 597 value (-0.585). Examining the MAD's overall bias in relative terms, the economic
 598 dimension had the highest value (-0.797), while the institutional dimension had
 599 the lowest value (-0.209).

600

601 **Table 1.** Regional average of the total biases between the original IMRI and
 602 dimension scores and the median or MAD obtained in the Monte Carlo analysis.

Dimensions	Number of factors	Median (absolute average)	Median (relative average)	MAD (absolute average)	MAD (relative average)
Social	9	1.066	0.118	-3.459	-0.384
Economic	6	-4.016	-0.669	-4.783	-0.797
Ecosystem	9	0.463	0.051	-3.905	-0.434
Physical	8	-1.785	-0.223	-3.461	-0.433
Institutional	4	1.072	0.268	-0.834	-0.209
Cultural	1	0.167	0.167	-0.585	-0.585
IMRI	37	-4.785	-0.129	-13.313	-0.360

603

604

605 Total bias values derived from IMRI scores can be disaggregated for each
 606 municipality of interest (Fig. 5). There are six main categories of total bias that
 607 discriminate between positive (pinkish) and negative (bluish) values. Additionally,
 608 the hue intensity is related to the total bias value within each colour spectrum.
 609 Therefore, brighter colours are associated with fewer overall biases (i.e., a low
 610 category), whereas darker colours are related to higher total biases (i.e., a high
 611 category; Tate, 2013). The low category included total bias values up to the
 612 median or 50th percentile for both positive and negative values; the moderate

613 category entailed total bias values up to the 80th percentile; and the high category
614 contained the most extreme total bias values (Aroca-Jiménez et al., 2022). Each
615 municipality's text label identifies the resilience category in which it was included,
616 which facilitates the visual identification of connections between the IMRI and
617 overall bias categories.

618

619 Accordingly, municipalities with a very high IMRI score had a negative and low
620 overall bias in comparison to the median (in 45.5% of cases) and the MAD (in
621 72.7% of cases). In addition, 58.3% of municipalities with a very low IMRI score
622 exhibited a statistically significant and negative overall bias with respect to the
623 median and the MAD. Fig. 5 demonstrated that municipalities with a highly
624 positive bias from the median have a very high IMRI value (in all cases), while
625 municipalities with a large negative bias had a very low IMRI value (in 77.8% of
626 cases). Regarding bias from the MAD, municipalities with a large positive bias
627 have a very high IMRI value (in all cases), while municipalities with a large
628 negative bias have a very low IMRI value (in 63.6% of cases). As determined by
629 the Monte Carlo analysis, Fig. S6–S11 in the supplementary material show, for
630 each municipality, the overall bias values between the original scores of the
631 different dimensions and the median or MAD.

632

633

634 **Fig. 5.** Total bias values of the original IMRI scores from the median (a) and MAD
 635 (b) obtained in the Monte Carlo analysis for each municipality of interest.

636

637 Concerning the analysis of the robustness of the originally defined resilience
638 categories, Table 2 displays the average probability (in %) of changes in these
639 reference resilience categories when employing the statistics derived from the
640 Monte Carlo analysis (i.e., medians and MADs) instead of the original values of
641 the resilience factors and their respective weights for all the municipalities under
642 consideration. It is assumed that the index's robustness is high when the
643 probability of maintaining stable index categories is likewise high.

644

645 In relation to the median, the physical dimension had the highest probability that
646 its resilience category would not change (70.8%), although this might change with
647 a probability of 29.2%, especially if its category is increased (21.4%). The cultural
648 dimension, on the other hand, had the lowest probability of its resilience
649 categories remaining unaltered (19.3%), with an overall probability of change of
650 80.7%, divided pretty much equally between cases in which they would rise
651 (42.1%) and situations in which they would decline (38.6%).

652

653 Examining the MAD statistic revealed a similar pattern. Again, the physical
654 dimension had the highest probability that its resilience categories would remain
655 unchanged (70.4%), while the probability that they will change is just 29.6%,
656 mostly via increase (25.7%). The cultural dimension had the lowest probability of
657 preserving its resilience categories (19.3%). In this case, the probability of change
658 is 80.7%, with the possibility of an increase (61.4%) clearly outweighing the
659 possibility of decrease (19.3%). Based on an examination of the data for the IMRI
660 categories, both the median (stability probability of 85.3%) and standard deviation
661 (stability probability of 81.2%) are very stable. These categories would alter with

662 a probability of 14.7% if the median is utilized and 18.8% if the MAD is considered.

663 Nevertheless, the probability of the resilience category increasing is greater in

664 both cases (11.0% and 15.4%, respectively).

665

666 **Table 2.** Mean probability (%) of changes in resilience categories when
667 considering the median or MAD obtained in the Monte Carlo analysis instead of
668 the original IMRI and dimension scores.

Dimensions	Median			MAD		
	Decrease (%)	Unchanged (%)	Increase (%)	Decrease (%)	Unchanged (%)	Increase (%)
Social	13.7	68.9	17.4	6.7	59.6	33.7
Economic	14.3	55.4	30.3	8.8	49.9	41.4
Ecosystem	12.6	70.0	17.4	7.2	64.7	28.1
Physical	7.8	70.8	21.4	3.9	70.4	25.7
Institutional	21.4	67.4	11.2	12.6	57.9	29.5
Cultural	38.6	19.3	42.1	19.3	19.3	61.4
IMRI	3.7	85.3	11.0	3.4	81.2	15.4

669

670

671 The probability of changes in IMRI categories, disaggregated by municipality, is

672 shown in Fig. 6. As illustrated in Fig. 4, the hue of each municipality represents

673 its resilience category as determined by the original IMRI scores. Moreover, the

674 pie chart for each municipality depicts the probability that the resilience category

675 will stay steady (grey), rise (dark blue), or decline (light blue). In municipalities

676 with a very high resilience, the average probability of a category remaining

677 unaltered is 96.5% when using the median and 97.8% when using the MAD. In

678 municipalities with very low resilience, the probability that this category would not

679 change is 90.5% when using the median and 89.1% when utilizing the MAD.

680 Moreover, the resilience of municipalities where the probability of not changing

681 categories is 100% is often rather high, when the median (60.0%) and the MAD

682 (62.5%) are included. Fig. S12-S17 included in the supplementary material show

683 the probability of changes in the categories originally assigned to each resilience
684 dimension.

685

686

687 **Fig. 6.** Probability of changes (%) in the IMRI categories when considering the
688 median (a) or MAD (b) obtained in the Monte Carlo analysis instead of the
689 baseline scores for each municipality of interest.

690 Regarding the sensitivity analysis, Fig. 7 depicts the impact of changes to the
 691 scores of the IMRI's resilience factors and weights on the index's final score. The
 692 vertical axis indicates each factor and weight considered, along with the
 693 corresponding dimension in parentheses. In contrast, the horizontal axis
 694 illustrates the range of IMRI results. Those factors or weights at the top of the
 695 sensitivity tornado plot have a greater impact on the IMRI scores than those at
 696 the bottom. The width of each bar is calculated using the 5th (orange bar) and
 697 95th percentiles (blue bar) of the scores for each factor or weight, while the
 698 median is used for the other factors or weights. Using the Monte Carlo analysis,
 699 the 5th and 95th percentiles, as well as the median, were determined. The cultural
 700 dimension, as well as its factor and weight, were excluded from the sensitivity
 701 analysis because its scores were not subject to any weighting factor (i.e., the
 702 weight assigned to this dimension was equal to 1, meaning that the original
 703 scores were not modified, which was not the case in the other dimensions).

704

705 **Fig. 7.** Sensitivity tornado plot shows the influence of variations in the scores of
 706 resilience factors and weights on the final IMRI scores.

707 Analyzing in detail the upper part of Fig. 7 (i.e., the top 10 elements of the
708 sensitivity tornado plot), the most significant resilience factors on IMRI scores are
709 the economic and institutional dimensions, which accounted for 40% of each of
710 these upper portions. Examining the components at the bottom of the sensitivity
711 tornado plot revealed, however, that the weights of all dimensions except the
712 cultural dimension are present. Regardless of how the 10 resilience components
713 at the bottom of the tornado plot are evaluated (i.e., notwithstanding the weights),
714 it is evident that the dimension with the highest representation, with 50% of the
715 components, is the physical dimension. Fig. S18-S22 of the supplementary
716 material provide the sensitivity tornado plots for each resilience dimension.

717

718 *3.3 Regional spatial patterns of resilience*

719 The optimal model was the one that considered five different municipal clusters
720 based on the lowest AIC value. According to the parameters of this model, all
721 dimensions were statistically significant (p -value < 0.05) in identifying municipal
722 clusters related to the identification of spatial patterns of resilience. Fig. 8 displays
723 the cluster to which each municipality that participated in the resilience analysis
724 belongs (Fig. 8a). The radar chart, in contrast, revealed the profile associated
725 with each municipality cluster (Fig. 8b). The radar chart depicts the standard
726 deviations from the mean for each municipality cluster (distinct line colour for
727 each cluster) and for each resilience dimension (represented at the vertices of
728 the radar chart). Positive standard deviation values implied above-average social,
729 economic, ecosystem, physical, institutional, or cultural resilience (i.e., more
730 resilient municipalities), while negative values suggested below-average
731 resilience (i.e., less resilient municipalities).

732 Cluster 1 is comprised of 16 municipalities (28.1% of the total) and is defined by
733 high cultural resilience but poor ecosystem resilience. Cluster 2 is composed of
734 16 municipalities (28.1% of the total). It has the lowest economic resilience, the
735 lowest cultural resilience, and the highest ecosystem resilience. 11 municipalities
736 (19.3 % of the total) comprised cluster 3, which had the lowest scores for social,
737 ecosystem, institutional, and economic resilience. Cluster 4 was formed by 8
738 municipalities (14% of the total) and had the highest physical resilience values,
739 the highest economic resilience values, the lowest institutional resilience values,
740 and the lowest cultural resilience values. Cluster 5 included 6 municipalities
741 (10.5% of the total) and had the highest levels of social, ecosystem, institutional,
742 and cultural resilience, along with high levels of ecosystem resilience and the
743 lowest levels of physical resilience.

744

745

746 **Fig. 8.** Outputs of the Latent Class Cluster Analysis (LCCA): municipal clusters
 747 identified (a) and profiles of the five identified clusters (b).

748

749 Table 3 displays the results of the comparison between the means of the various
750 dimension scores for each pair of clusters, identifying the cases in which the
751 differences were statistically significant (p-value < 0.05). In Table 3, the difference
752 column summarizes the comparison between the various municipal clusters. This
753 comparison is based on the mean values obtained for each cluster, which are
754 accessible in Table S7 of the supplementary material. Thus, one of the most
755 notable differences is that the urban areas included in the fifth cluster are more
756 resilient than the others in terms of social, economic, institutional, and cultural
757 dimensions.

758

759 Finally, we proved that there were statistically significant differences in the mean
760 IMRI scores of the selected municipality clusters. Levene's test revealed that the
761 required assumption of variance homogeneity for an ANOVA was not satisfied (p-
762 value ≤ 0.05), making it necessary to use Welch's test. This test and its associated
763 post-hoc test (i.e., the Games-Howell test) confirmed the existence of statistically
764 significant differences between the mean IMRI scores of cluster 1 (0.063), and
765 clusters 3 (-0.188) and 4 (-0.156), with cluster 1 municipalities exhibiting greater
766 resilience than clusters 3 and 4. There were also statistically significant
767 differences between the mean IMRI scores of clusters 5 (0.567) and 3 (-0.188),
768 displaying more resilience in cluster 5. Cluster 5 municipalities (0.567) were the
769 most resilient, based on the mean scores for all clusters, while cluster 3
770 municipalities were the least resilient (-0.188).

771

772

773

774 **Table 3.** Pairwise cluster comparison of the mean scores obtained for the different
 775 dimensions of resilience in search of statistically significant differences. The
 776 identification of differences was based on the Wald statistic.

Models for indicators	Paired comp. ^a	Wald	p-value	Differences ^b
Social	1-2	0.224	0.640	C5 > C2, C1, C4, C3 C2 > C3 C1 > C3
	1-3	4.276	0.039*	
	1-4	0.930	0.330	
	1-5	12.308	0.000*	
	2-3	5.405	0.020*	
	2-4	1.820	0.180	
	2-5	9.876	0.002*	
	3-4	2.149	0.140	
	3-5	19.561	0.000*	
	4-5	14.838	0.000*	
Economic	1-2	18.311	0.000*	C5 > C1, C3, C2 C4 > C3, C2 C1 > C2
	1-3	2.862	0.091	
	1-4	2.704	0.100	
	1-5	4.327	0.038*	
	2-3	1.778	0.180	
	2-4	24.214	0.000*	
	2-5	34.975	0.000*	
	3-4	7.842	0.005*	
	3-5	11.043	0.001*	
	4-5	0.004	0.950	
Ecosystem	1-2	33.100	0.000*	C2 > C4, C1, C3 C5 > C1, C3
	1-3	0.048	0.830	
	1-4	1.001	0.320	
	1-5	7.561	0.006*	
	2-3	43.441	0.000*	
	2-4	16.555	0.000*	
	2-5	0.578	0.450	
	3-4	1.874	0.170	
	3-5	9.106	0.003*	
	4-5	3.449	0.063	
Physical	1-2	3.431	0.064	C4 > C3, C1, C5
	1-3	0.090	0.760	
	1-4	16.820	0.000*	
	1-5	0.989	0.320	
	2-3	0.882	0.350	
	2-4	3.782	0.052	
	2-5	2.806	0.094	
	3-4	4.654	0.031*	
	3-5	1.254	0.260	
	4-5	5.376	0.020*	
Institutional	1-2	0.696	0.400	C5 > C2, C1, C4, C3 C2 > C4, C3 C1 > C4, C3
	1-3	24.291	0.000*	
	1-4	6.209	0.013*	
	1-5	19.090	0.000*	
	2-3	21.289	0.000*	
	2-4	9.481	0.002*	
	2-5	14.613	0.000*	
	3-4	0.766	0.380	
	3-5	31.949	0.000*	
	4-5	26.539	0.000*	
Cultural	1-2	11.206	0.001*	C5 > C3 > C2 > C4 C1 > C3 > C2 > C4
	1-3	5.419	0.020*	
	1-4	29.723	0.000*	
	1-5	1.394	0.240	
	2-3	6.913	0.009*	
	2-4	4.863	0.027*	
	2-5	12.337	0.000*	
	3-4	156.819	0.000*	
	3-5	7.322	0.007*	
	4-5	21.501	0.000*	

777 **Notes.** Paired comp.: paired comparison. ^aNumbers correspond to the different clusters
 778 of municipalities identified by the LCCA. ^bThe mean values of all clusters for all
 779 dimensions are given in Table S7 of the supplementary material. *Statistically significant
 780 differences (p -value<0.05).

781

782 **4. Discussion**

783 This research describes how to create and validate an Integrated
784 Multidimensional Resilience Index (IMRI) in flash flood-prone urban areas. To that
785 purpose, a completely multidimensional method to characterize resilience across
786 all resilience dimensions (i.e., social, economic, ecosystem, physical,
787 institutional, and cultural) was adopted.

788

789 *4.1 Factors explaining inherent resilience*

790 Resilience analysis is still handled in a fragmented manner. This research
791 proposes using multidimensional approaches to identify the underlying features
792 that determine resilience and provide specific strategies to build resilience since
793 results can be disaggregated by dimensions.

794

795 Urban areas with the highest IMRI values are those with the highest social and
796 cultural scores. In terms of resource availability and population awareness of
797 flood risk, these urban areas are well-equipped to handle emergencies. This
798 implies that both individuals and the community can respond properly to flash
799 floods, limiting their effects (Khan et al., 2022). In these urban areas individuals
800 are rooted, social networks are extensive, and the urban environment is
801 protected. This reduces the population's recovery time after a flash flood and
802 helps them adapt to future events (Parsons et al., 2021). These urban areas are
803 also home to families with a medium-high level of education, which usually
804 translates into an acceptable economic level and stability, making them more
805 likely to recover from a flash flood (Sherrieb et al., 2010).

806

807 Regarding the cultural dimension, the most resilient municipalities have well-
808 preserved cultural assets and support for cultural activities. Tourism and
809 commercial activities related to cultural heritage can bring considerable sums of
810 money into municipal coffers; therefore, well-preserved cultural assets can assist
811 in the recovery capacity of urban areas (Arrighi et al., 2022). Cultural events can
812 also strengthen social cohesiveness and the community's resilience to flash
813 floods (Hernández-Morcillo et al., 2013).

814

815 Besides, municipalities with the lowest IMRI values have the lowest social and
816 institutional scores. On the social dimension, this means that urban areas with
817 the poorest basic infrastructure and services, such as health centres, sports and
818 recreational facilities, and internet access, are the least resilient. Governments
819 should ensure access to this essential infrastructure and these services to
820 decrease social inequities that reduce resilience (Wyss et al., 2022). Many flash
821 flood-prone municipalities in Castilla y León, which are peripheral, suffer from this
822 (Marzi et al., 2019). However, governments can use the internet to raise
823 awareness of flash flood risk, making internet access a crucial part of community
824 adaptation to extreme events (Marzi et al., 2019). These urban areas have the
825 least social cohesion, as seen by the lack of social and religious organizations
826 and low voter turnout in elections and social movements. Public authorities
827 should involve the public in evacuation drills and risk communication campaigns
828 to help communities cope with, recover from, and adapt to flash floods (Rana et
829 al., 2021). These localities also feature high dependency rates, many single-
830 person households, low education, and people with disabilities. These issues can
831 lead to social isolation since many of these people cannot leave the flooded area

832 on their own, which hampers evacuation (Qasim et al., 2016). The elderly may
833 also be injured if their household work assistance is disrupted (Boon, 2014).
834 Conversely, a low educational level limits the ability to interpret flood warning
835 signs and obtain recovery aids, making flash floods harder to handle and recover
836 from (Cutter et al., 2010).

837

838 In terms of institutional dimension, the least resilient municipalities have no local
839 flood risk management plan. These local plans should include resilience building
840 strategies to reduce flood risk, and relevant agencies should encourage their
841 development (Bodoque et al., 2016). The unavailability of local flood risk and
842 emergency management plans often implies distrust between communities and
843 involved institutions and poor risk communication by local authorities, which
844 weakens resilience (Marzi et al., 2019). These municipalities also invest less in
845 education, scientific research, and emergency management. A core competence
846 of governments is emergency management, so flood risk agencies should equip
847 these areas with emergency systems to respond to flash floods (Oriangi et al.,
848 2019). Community preparedness and recovery from flash floods can be
849 enhanced by flood risk education and awareness (Khan et al., 2022).

850

851 *4.2 Sources of IMRI uncertainty and sensitivity*

852 IMRI outputs were internally validated using Monte Carlo uncertainty and
853 sensitivity analyses. External validation methods using ancillary datasets (e.g.,
854 flood-related losses, fatalities, or affected people) have been used to assess
855 indices quality. However, these approaches are hardly applicable to flash flood-
856 prone areas since extra information for validation is rarely available because flash

857 flood events occur in relatively limited areas rather than across a region
858 (Bakkensen et al., 2017).

859 Several papers that employ internal validation approaches also do so locally,
860 analysing the effect of changing a single input parameter on index scores (e.g.,
861 Marzi et al., 2019; Moreira et al., 2021). In this research, uncertainty and
862 sensitivity were assessed globally by evaluating the overall variation produced in
863 the IMRI results when jointly considering the variation sources of all input
864 parameters, which is a more complete and reliable method than the local one
865 (Feizizadeh and Kienberger, 2017). This can assist decision-makers in
866 understanding index limits and integrating them with confidence in flash flood risk
867 management plans (Aroca-Jiménez et al., 2022).

868

869 In the uncertainty analysis, the median as an unbiased estimator of the central
870 tendency and the median absolute deviation (MAD) as an estimator of the
871 dispersion of the IMRI scores were utilized from among the various statistics
872 derived from the Monte Carlo method. The median has been previously used by
873 other authors (Tate, 2013; Nazeer and Bork, 2019). However, the MAD is not as
874 commonly used as the standard deviation (Feizizadeh and Kienberger, 2017) or
875 the variation coefficient (Tate, 2013). The results revealed a low bias between the
876 IMRI scores and the median and MAD from the Monte Carlo analysis,
877 demonstrating the IMRI's robustness. The economic dimension accumulated the
878 most bias between the original scores and the median and MAD. On this basis,
879 the quality of the economic dimension indicators should be reviewed.

880

881 IMRI scores showed an 85.3% and 81.2% probability of not changing the
882 resilience category when using the median and MAD, respectively, from the
883 Monte Carlo analysis, indicating excellent IMRI robustness. When examining the
884 results by dimension, the physical dimension had the most stable resilience
885 categories (i.e., 70.8% probability with respect to the median and 70.4%
886 probability with respect to the MAD), while the cultural dimension had the most
887 unstable categories (19.3% probability with respect to both the median and MAD).
888 This can be due to the fact that the cultural dimension had only one resilience
889 factor, which had a high degree of variability, and its scores were not influenced
890 by the weighting factor.

891

892 As indicated above, cultural dimension variability caused a wide range of IMRI
893 scores, which affected sensitivity analysis outcomes. This masked the results for
894 the rest of the resilience factors in the other dimensions; hence, it was decided to
895 remove the cultural dimension from the IMRI sensitivity analysis to better assess
896 the effect of the variability of the other factors on the IMRI scores. This could
897 generate some confusion among decision-makers about resilience index
898 outcomes. Thereby, the cultural dimension should be better characterized by
899 adding proxy variables. After removing the cultural dimension from the sensitivity
900 tornado plot, the institutional dimension had the biggest impact on IMRI scores.
901 This means that institutional decisions can have a major impact on the resilience
902 of the urban areas included in this work; therefore, this type of approach would
903 help flood risk agencies make the best flood risk reduction decisions (Wyss et al.,
904 2022).

905

906 *4.3 Definition of regional resilience-building strategies*

907 Latent Class Cluster Analysis revealed regional resilience patterns (LCCA). This
908 allowed the formulation of tailored strengthening resilience strategies for each
909 cluster of municipalities, which can help to improve flash flood risk management
910 plans and economic resource allocation (Aroca-Jiménez et al., 2020, 2022).

911

912 Ecosystem resilience was the lowest in urban areas in the first cluster. Here,
913 resilience recovery strategies should focus on restoring floodplains and their
914 ecosystem services using nature-based solutions (NbSs) with substantial
915 community engagement (Kelly-Quinn et al., 2021).

916

917 The second cluster includes the least economically resilient communities.
918 Consequently, resilience strategies should focus on supporting investment in
919 measures to fix population so they can recover employment and reactivate their
920 economy (Parsons et al., 2021). Individual resilience strategies should consider
921 a system of economic benefits based on the adoption of self-protection measures
922 by the population exposed to flash floods (Highfield and Brody, 2013).

923

924 The third cluster's urban areas are the least resilient to flash floods due to low
925 social, ecosystem, and institutional resilience. To improve social capital,
926 awareness, and perception of flood risk in these municipalities, relevant local
927 agencies should initiate risk communication campaigns to encourage public
928 engagement in decision-making, which can improve flood risk management
929 (Boon, 2014). This can also boost institutional resilience in these areas by
930 increasing public trust in institutions (Marzi et al., 2019). More investment in

931 emergency management and better coordination between local, regional, and
932 national authorities should accompany this (Blázquez et al., 2021).

933 Cultural resilience is the lowest in municipalities included in the fourth cluster.
934 Thus, these areas should improve the protection of their cultural heritage by
935 extending a buffer area around them as much as feasible and boosting the
936 promotion of their cultural assets to raise tourist attractiveness, which would also
937 provide indirect economic benefits (Arrighi et al., 2022).

938

939 Finally, municipalities included in the fifth cluster have the lowest physical
940 resilience. These areas should encourage people self-protection to avoid leaving
941 flood protection solely to local administrations (Bodoque et al., 2016). In addition,
942 these localities need an updated evacuation plan so that residents know what to
943 do and where to relocate during a flash flood to mitigate damages (Qasim et al.,
944 2016). Municipalities should use this shortcoming to adopt nature-based
945 solutions instead of grey infrastructures, which may increase flood risk. (Wyss et
946 al., 2022).

947

948 A temporal monitoring of the effectiveness of the implementation of the measures
949 proposed above, besides offering a view on the temporal evolution of social,
950 economic, ecosystem, physical, institutional, and cultural resilience in the
951 different municipalities included in the analysis, would provide valuable
952 information on which measures and strategies have the greatest positive impact
953 on the territory, thereby making urban areas more resilient to flash floods.

954

955

956 *4.4 Advantages and limitations of the methodological approach*

957 Although there is no consensus in the literature on the best method for measuring
958 resilience, index-based approaches are generally utilized since they allow the
959 integration of multi-thematic indicators into a single value to represent such a
960 complex and not directly quantifiable feature as resilience (Birkmann et al., 2013).
961 This methodology allows end-users of these indices to know which social,
962 economic, ecosystem, physical, institutional, and cultural elements determine
963 each urban area's resilience, thus enabling them to take the required actions to
964 build or increase resilience to reduce flood risk (Hagenlocher et al., 2018). In
965 urban mountain areas prone to flash floods, this method helps allocate scarce
966 economic resources more efficiently (Marzi et al., 2019).

967

968 Index-based approaches also simplify the phenomenon being measured, making
969 knowledge transmission to non-expert stakeholders easier and raising
970 community awareness of flash flood risk (Kotzee and Reyers, 2016). The
971 baseline information used to generate resilience indices is usually released
972 openly and often updated, allowing for spatial and temporal monitoring of the
973 study area's resilience. The above would also help assess resilience recovery
974 and strengthening measures' efficacy (Cutter et al., 2010). These indices would
975 indeed help measure compliance with other policy objectives like climate change
976 adaptation or sustainable development (Marzi et al., 2019). This methodology is
977 also adaptable to other spatial contexts or natural hazards by adapting the
978 resilience indicators utilized in this research. In such cases, the scale of analysis
979 and management should coincide, otherwise the resilience index would not be

980 representative and the resulting resilience strengthening strategies would not be
981 effective (Frazier et al., 2013).

982

983 Resilience indices' quality mostly depends on the input data and methodological
984 decisions used to generate them (Moreira et al., 2021). As data in urban areas
985 prone to flash flooding is limited, either because statistical information is not
986 provided at that scale or because it is collected from small samples, the
987 representativeness of input data is even more important (Cortès et al., 2018).
988 Regarding the methodology, decisions made to construct resilience indices entail
989 some subjectivity, which introduces uncertainty into the assessment of resilience
990 scores (Beccari, 2016). Resilience factor weights are one of the most subjective
991 index construction decisions (Nazeer and Bork, 2019). So, some authors argue
992 that, in the absence of objective data on which indicators best explain resilience,
993 it is preferable to give all factors the same weight (Cutter et al., 2010). However,
994 other authors claim that not all resilience factors are comparable, especially when
995 their number of variables and variance explained vary (Liu and Li, 2016). This
996 study proposes a weighting approach based on the tolerance statistic to adjust
997 for the correlation between the factors that make up each resilience dimension
998 and the index's overrepresentation of particular characteristics (Aroca-Jiménez
999 et al., 2022).

1000

1001 **5. Conclusions**

1002 This research provides a novel, comprehensively holistic approach for regionally
1003 constructing and validating an Integrated Multidimensional Resilience Index
1004 (IMRI) in flash flood-prone urban areas. This was done by considering all relevant

1005 dimensions (social, economic, ecosystem, physical, institutional, and cultural).
1006 This approach allows the identification of the urban-social systems' underlying
1007 characteristics that govern resilience, which allows the creation of distinct
1008 resilience recovery and strengthening strategies for each dimension. The
1009 development of resilience indices also helps integrate flood risk reduction into
1010 other policy areas like sustainable development or river ecosystem conservation
1011 and restoration, reconciling and achieving the objectives of recent policy
1012 frameworks like the Sendai Framework, the European Green Deal, or the 2030
1013 Agenda. The internal validation of the IMRI through a global analysis of
1014 uncertainty and sensitivity based on the Monte Carlo method has allowed us to
1015 evaluate the ranges of variability of the index input parameters and assess how
1016 these influence the IMRI and the dimension scores, which has helped us
1017 determine the IMRI's robustness and main sources of variation. This makes
1018 decision-makers aware of index limitations, which boosts confidence in the IMRI
1019 outputs and makes resilience indices easier to include in flood risk management
1020 plans. Finally, Latent Class Cluster Analysis identified spatial patterns of
1021 resilience at the regional scale, enabling the tailoring of resilience-building
1022 methods for each municipality cluster. This improves flash flood risk management
1023 plans and economic resource allocation for flash flood risk reduction, as well as
1024 assisting decision-makers in prioritizing actions and resources during a flash
1025 flood event, ultimately decreasing resulting losses.

1026

1027 **CRediT authorship contribution statement**

1028 **E. Aroca-Jiménez:** Conceptualization; Data curation; Formal analysis;
1029 Investigation; Methodology; Validation; Visualization; Writing - original draft. **J. M.**

1030 **Bodoque:** Conceptualization; Funding acquisition; Investigation; Methodology;
1031 Project administration; Supervision; Writing - review & editing. **J. A. García:**
1032 Formal analysis; Methodology; Writing - review & editing.

1033

1034 **Data availability**

1035 Original resilience indicator dataset used in this study is available at Zenodo
1036 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.7540559>)

1037

1038 **Declaration of competing interest**

1039 The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

1040

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1045

1046 **Appendix A. Supplementary data**

1047 Supplementary data to this article can be found online at

1048

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